

PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF BLACK PEOPLE'S MUSIC CREATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific-theoretical significance of Karakalpak folk music in improving the professional training of future music culture teachers.

Key words: Karakalpak folk music creation, music culture, professional competence, methodology.

Music has the ability to influence the moral and ethical aspects of the soul. As long as music has such characteristics, it should be included among the means of educating young people." The role of our musical heritage is also important in this regard, as the national program requires the training of highly qualified personnel who respond to highly moral and ethical students. While getting acquainted with the heritage of Uzbek folk music in music and culture classes, we learn about the historical path of the hardworking people, traditions, rituals, friendship, heroism, love for the Motherland, love - loyalty, justice. we will have a broad understanding of.

According to the great physician Ibn Sina, patients were meditated with the help of pleasant music. He said that the earlier the formation of children's inclination and need for fine art begins, the more useful it is. He writes in his book "Ash Shifo": "A number of useful tools for the body of young children include physical education, as well as songs and music that are sung while the child is being pampered. Depending on the mastery of these two things, the child will develop an inclination towards physical exercises and music, one of which is related to money and the other to the heart.

"Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level". A person can be professional in his field, but it is difficult to have professional competence in solving problems. In several scientific studies, researchers have touched on the concepts of "professional competence" from a pedagogical and psychological point of view. For example, in her research, A.K. Markova mentions that the professional competence of a pedagogue consists of 4 structural foundations.

- ❖ Social competence;
- ❖ Personal competence;

- ❖ Individual competence;
- ❖ Special competence.

Future pedagogues having the competencies listed above is one of the important aspects in their formation as highly qualified pedagogues. Considering each of these competencies specifically for future music teachers will help them understand the importance of improving their professional competence.

Social competence means being active in social relations, possessing various skills, being able to communicate, knowing the rules of ethics of one's profession, competitiveness, being able to arouse social interest in one's specialty, standing out in the team with one's personal professional qualities. It is known that music teachers, like other pedagogical fields, can create a classroom environment during the lesson, establish direct communication with students, determine the content and effectiveness of the lesson. The formation of this competence in future music teachers is also necessary to establish a dialogue between the teacher and the student, through which the teacher can deliver practical science to the students in a correct and understandable way. will help.

Personal competence is the achievement of professional growth, increasing the level of qualification, showing one's inner capabilities during professional activity, universality, creative direction. The fact that future music teachers have a creative aspect, are considered representatives of the world of music, and demonstrate their skills and talents in any activity of the lesson increases the interest of this class in science and ensures a high level of mastery.

Individual competence - self-management, professional development, ability to accept oneself professionally, organization, self-development through various experiences, defining one's own path in professional growth and creating innovations. Each topic is unique and different in content, which requires a special approach of the teacher to the lessons. It is natural that future music teachers have and develop this competence, which ensures the content of the lesson, the wealth of news and, as a result, meaningfulness.

Special competence is to understand the essence of one's profession, to achieve high results, to prepare for the organization of professional and pedagogical activities, to solve tasks rationally, to realistically evaluate the results of the activity. Special competence includes several other competence qualities: psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative, communicative competence. According to Markov's theory, a student should possess several abilities related to music, in addition to having the professional competencies

that we mentioned above. The professional competence of a future music teacher is a set of professional and personal characteristics that allow successful implementation of professional and pedagogical activities. Taking into account that the activity of a music teacher includes various components, future music teachers should have the skills of pedagogy, choir mastery, musicology, performance, vocal abilities, and lecturing skills.

The science of music culture is related to other disciplines, and each of these disciplines is important in connecting music to life and making lessons meaningful. In schools, music lessons are conducted in primary and secondary grades, and "music lessons in primary grades consist of five types of activities:

1. Singing in chorus.
2. Music literacy.
3. Listening to music.
4. Performing movements to the music.
5. It is to accompany children on musical instruments.

In middle classes, there are 3 types of activities. When organizing the lesson process through the types of activities, the teacher himself must have these skills and be able to deliver creative processes to children without difficulties. A pedagogue acquires skills in activities from his student years. Therefore, among the interpersonal relations, artistic thinking, verbal explanation, and professional-diagnostic competencies that we have listed above, the most important competencies that future music teachers are required to have are the following:

Competence in singing - vocal and choir are important as students learn music in a practical way in lessons. Since singing in a choir is one of the activities of the music culture lesson, the teacher must have a beautiful, pleasant voice, and sing the vocal piece with pure intonation. Because the children sing in imitation of the teacher. Not only to sing well and cleanly, but also to know the vocal range of students, special attention should be paid to this in teaching singing. In elementary school students, the voice range is from the first octave of C to the second octave of C.

Stages of development of the history of Karakalpak national music art. In order for young people to mature spiritually, it is always the supreme goal of musicologists, scientists and intellectuals to deeply teach them the national music works of their people along with world music, to accompany them in the lives of young people, and from the main directions of propaganda work. has come. Of course, representatives of the art and culture sphere should be

individuals with high intellectual potential. The role and importance of national music art in understanding our national culture and identity is incomparable. Music is an art form that has divine power. It has a significant impact on the spiritual strengthening of the human heart and the formation of a perfect person. He is always a creative companion of mankind, helps and comforts him in times of joy, happiness, even when his heart is full of sorrow and depression. Music is a type of art that creates an image with different sounds and has an ideological and emotional content. The science of music aesthetics studies these cases. Because it is a science that studies the broad and deep essence of music art, artistic forms and methods of absorption.

There is no denying that Uzbek music and Karakalpak music have a place in the world music culture, they are very important. At this point, one direction of Karakalpak folk music is the song genre. The basis of folk songs sounds like a melody from the distant past, reflects the life experiences of the people, and is recognized as a cultural heritage.

The people expressed their lifestyle rich in various historical events, spiritual experiences and folk psychology through songs. In the songs, the reality of the life of ordinary people can be seen. Such works of art, created during difficult times, have not lost their value until now. The people treated their songs with respect and appreciated them. It is no exaggeration to say that there are countless examples of oral folk art that provided spiritual support to our ancestors. Doctor of philology N. Daugaraev said: "The people of Karakalpak could not live without songs, speech and oral poetry, both in their sad days and in their happy days."

Honorable President Sh. Mirziyoyev also has great love for Karakalpak art. At one of the meetings: "... young people of Karakalpakstan very actively participated in various events and holidays held at our institute. Especially when we went to Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions to pick cotton, after work, in the evenings, around the campfire, we all admired when our Karakalpak girls and boys read poems by poets such as Kunkhoja, Ajiniyaz, Berdaq, sang and danced. I still remember very well when I heard the Karakalpak folk songs "Bozatov", "Aydinlar", "Dem Bermes" for the first time and I felt as if I was somehow enchanted... Karakalpak land is in its own world "He continues to amaze us all with his unique and unique art," he said.

Indeed, Karakalpak national music art has been polished for centuries and has reached us as a masterpiece without losing its melodiousness and the brilliance of its heartfelt lyrics. Now, the task of bringing these works into the life and

education of young people, and being able to listen to young people, is literally both a debt and a duty, and at the same time, an honorable task for young artists like us.

As we analyze the issues of studying Karakalpak national music, we understand that the scientific works and research processes that should be studied in the field are not yet at the level of demand. We lack specialists. We need to support the existing experts to a certain extent. If we take into account that it has not been more than 20 years since the opening of higher education institutions related to the field in our country, we believe that our mature scientists-intellectuals who will perfectly study the field will grow up. This is the demand of the times!

One of the main goals of the educational system is to prepare future music teachers for spiritual and educational activities. From the above comments, we can say that the role of the science of music culture in the education system is very important. In order for music culture teachers to be active in spiritual and educational work, they are given the necessary knowledge and skills in higher education institutions.

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